

POSTER PRESENTATION

POTENTIAL OF LIGNIN AS AN ADSORBENT FOR THE REMOVAL AND DETECTION OF HORMONES FROM WATER

Dragana V. Lukić^{1*}, Vesna M. Vasić¹, Taciana Guarnieri², Geórgia Labuto², Vanessa J. Pereira^{3,4}, João Crespo^{4,5}, Nataša Đurišić-Mladenović¹

¹University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Technology Novi Sad, Blvd. cara Lazara 1, 21000 Novi Sad, Serbia
**dkukic@uns.ac.rs*

²Universidade Federal de São Paulo, Diadema, SP, CEP 09972-270, Brazil

³iBET, Instituto de Biologia Experimental e Tecnológica, Apartado 12, 2781-901 Oeiras, Portugal

⁴Instituto de Tecnologia Química e Biológica António Xavier, Universidade Nova de Lisboa, Av. da República, 2780-157 Oeiras, Portugal

⁵NOVA School of Science and Technology, Universidade NOVA de Lisboa, Portugal

The occurrence of hormones in aquatic environments has become a significant environmental concern. Their presence in water bodies may pose risks to aquatic organisms and human health. Monitoring of these contaminants is crucial for assessing exposure and potential risks, and one effective approach involves the use of passive samplers, which enable continuous monitoring over extended periods.

In this study, the potential of lignin as a sorbent for hormones was evaluated through batch adsorption experiments. A synthetic mixture containing approximately 500 µg/L of hormones was prepared as model water. 50 mL of the model solution was mixed with either 60 mg or 200 mg of kraft lignin derived from nutshells for up to 72 hours. Samples (1 mL) were taken at 24, 48, and 72 hours. The initial and residual concentrations of β -estradiol and α -ethinylestradiol in water solutions before and after the contact with lignin were determined using HPLC-DAD/FL.

Lignin demonstrated relatively slow adsorption for β -estradiol, with similar adsorption efficiencies (68%) observed for both lignin doses after 24 hours. Equilibrium was reached after 48 hours, with an adsorption efficiency of 81%. In contrast, α -ethinylestradiol showed higher adsorption efficiency, reaching 80% for the 60 mg dose and 89% for the 200 mg dose after 24 hours. Maximum adsorption of 90% and 95%, respectively was achieved after 48 hours. However, prolonged contact time (72 hours) slightly decreased adsorption in both cases.

Moreover, given its proven adsorption capacity, lignin was further evaluated for potential integration into passive samplers by subjecting the saturated material to extraction. To fulfill the role of passive samplers in monitoring natural water resources, the extraction process must enable quantitative and reproducible isolation of previously adsorbed hormones, so that the concentration of relevant pollutants can be accurately determined in the resulting extract. The lignin was packed into an empty cartridge between two frit discs, and methanol was used as the elution solvent. However, the resulting eluate was colored and contained fine particles, making it unsuitable for HPLC analysis. Since methanol proved ineffective for eluting the adsorbed hormones, alternative solvents should be tested to determine the suitability of lignin for use in passive samplers.

Keywords: adsorption, lignin, hydrochar, hormones, passive samplers

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